

MANIPAL CENTRE FOR EUROPEAN STUDIES

Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence in India-EU Interdisciplinary Studies - CLES

**CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING (CLIL)
IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT**

This is to certify that

Hafsha Banu

has participated in a 32-hour module on 'Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) in the Indian Context' conducted by the Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence - Manipal Centre for European Studies (MCES) held from July to November 2021 at Manipal Academy of Higher Education MAHE - an Institution of Eminence, Manipal.

PRIYA VIJAYKUMAR POOJARY
Lecturer
Manipal Centre for European Studies, MAHE

DR NEETA INAMDAR
Professor and Head
Manipal Centre for European Studies, MAHE

DR JAYASHREE K
Dean
Srinivas College of Education, Mangalore